

Comparing PHP FPM, PHP PPM, Nginx Unit, ReactPHP, and RoadRunner

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Abstract: This article compares the performance of several PHP application servers: PHP FPM, PHP PPM, Nginx Unit, ReactPHP, and RoadRunner. Tests were made with Symfony 4 and PHP 7.2 using Yandex Tank under different loads — 100, 500, 1000, and 10,000 requests per second. Each service was run in Docker containers with the same environment to get fair results. The study measured response time, CPU load, and memory usage. The results show that RoadRunner and ReactPHP give the fastest responses, while Nginx Unit offers a good balance between speed, stability, and easy setup. The article also provides detailed test configurations, performance charts, and recommendations for choosing the right PHP server for high-load projects.

Keywords: PHP, PHP-FPM, PHP-PPM, Nginx Unit, ReactPHP, RoadRunner, runtime performance, benchmark, concurrency

Testing was conducted using Yandex Tank.

Symfony 4 and PHP 7.2 were used as the application.

The goal was to compare the performance of the services under different loads and identify the optimal solution.

For convenience, everything was packaged into Docker containers and launched with docker-compose.

The source code is available [here](#).

All command examples mentioned in the article should be run from the project directory.

Application

The application runs on Symfony 4 and PHP 7.2.

It responds to only one route and returns:

- random number;
- environment;
- process pid;
- application name;
- php.ini variables.

Response example:

```
curl 'http://127.0.0.1:8000/' | python -m json.tool
{
  "env": "prod",
  "type": "php-fpm",
  "pid": 8,
  "random_num": 37264,
  "php": {
    "version": "7.2.12",
    "date.timezone": "Europe/Paris",
    "display_errors": "",
    "error_log": "/proc/self/fd/2",
    "error_reporting": "32767",
    "log_errors": "1",
    "memory_limit": "256M",
    "opcache.enable": "1",
    "opcache.max_accelerated_files": "20000",
    "opcache.memory_consumption": "256",
    "opcache.validate_timestamps": "0",
    "realpath_cache_size": "4096K",
    "realpath_cache_ttl": "600",
    "short_open_tag": ""
  }
}
```

Each container is configured with PHP:

- OPcache enabled;
- bootstrap cache configured using Composer;
- php.ini settings aligned with [Symfony's best practices](#).

Logs are written to stderr:
/config/packages/prod/monolog.yaml

```
monolog:
  handlers:
    main:
      type: stream
      path: "php://stderr"
      level: error
    console:
      type: console
```

The cache is stored in /dev/shm:
/src/Kernel.php

```
...
class Kernel extends BaseKernel
{
    public function getCacheDir()
    {
        if ($this->environment === 'prod') {
            return '/dev/shm/symfony-app/cache/' . $this->environment;
        } else {
            return $this->getProjectDir() . '/var/cache/' .
$this->environment;
        }
    }
}
...
```

Each docker-compose setup includes three main containers:

- nginx - reverse proxy server;
- app - the prepared application code with all dependencies;
- PHP FPM / Nginx Unit / RoadRunner / ReactPHP - the application server.

Request handling is limited to two application instances (equal to the number of CPU cores).

Services

PHP FPM

[PHP Process Manager](#). Written in C.

Pros:

- no need to monitor memory usage.
- no changes required in the application.

Cons:

- PHP initializes variables for every request.

Command to run the application with docker-compose:

```
cd docker/php-fpm && docker-compose up -d
```

PHP PPM

[PHP Process Manager](#). Written in PHP.

Pros:

- initializes variables once and reuses them afterward.
- no changes required in the application (ready-made modules available for Symfony, Laravel, Zend, and CakePHP).

Cons:

- requires memory management.

Command to run the application with docker-compose:

```
cd docker/php-ppm && docker-compose up -d
```

Ngix Unit

[Application Server by the Nginx Team](#). Written in C

Pros:

- configuration can be modified via HTTP API.
- allows running multiple instances of the same application with different configurations and language versions simultaneously.
- no need to manage memory.
- no changes required in the application.

Cons:

- PHP initializes variables for each request.

To pass environment variables from the Nginx Unit configuration file, you need to adjust the php.ini:

```
; Nginx Unit
variables_order=E
```

Command to run the application with docker-compose:

```
cd docker/nginx-unit && docker-compose up -d
```

React PHP

[Event-Driven Programming Library](#). Written in PHP.

Pros:

- the library allows you to write a server that initializes variables only once and then continues to reuse them.

Cons:

- requires custom server implementation.
- memory management is necessary.

If you use the `--reboot-kernel-after-request` flag for the worker, the Symfony Kernel will reinitialize for each request. With this approach, memory management is no longer required.

```
#!/usr/bin/env php

<?php

use App\Kernel;
use Symfony\Component\Debug\Debug;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Request;

require __DIR__ . '/../config/bootstrap.php';

$env    = $_SERVER['APP_ENV'] ?? $_ENV['APP_ENV'] ?? 'dev';
$debug  = (bool)($_SERVER['APP_DEBUG'] ?? $_ENV['APP_DEBUG'] ?? ('prod' !== $env));

if ($debug) {
    umask(0000);

    Debug::enable();
}

if ($trustedProxies = $_SERVER['TRUSTED_PROXIES'] ??
$_ENV['TRUSTED_PROXIES'] ?? false) {
    Request::setTrustedProxies(explode(',', $trustedProxies),
Request::HEADER_X_FORWARDED_ALL ^ Request::HEADER_X_FORWARDED_HOST);
```

```

}

if ($trustedHosts = $_SERVER['TRUSTED_HOSTS'] ?? $_ENV['TRUSTED_HOSTS'] ??
false) {
    Request::setTrustedHosts(explode(',', $trustedHosts));
}

$loop = React\EventLoop\Factory::create();
$kernel = new Kernel($env, $debug);
$kernel->boot();
$rebootKernelAfterRequest = in_array('--reboot-kernel-after-request',
$argv);

/** @var \Psr\Log\LoggerInterface $logger */
$logger = $kernel->getContainer()->get('logger');
$server = new React\Http\Server(function
(Psr\Http\Message\ServerRequestInterface $request) use ($kernel, $logger,
$rebootKernelAfterRequest) {

    $method = $request->getMethod();
    $headers = $request->getHeaders();
    $content = $request->getBody();
    $post = [];
    if (in_array(strtolower($method), ['POST', 'PUT', 'DELETE', 'PATCH'])
&&
        isset($headers['Content-Type']) && (0 ===
strpos($headers['Content-Type'], 'application/x-www-form-urlencoded'))
    ) {
        parse_str($content, $post);
    }
    $sfRequest = new Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Request(
        $request->getQueryParams(),
        $post,
        [],
        $request->getCookieParams(),
        $request->getUploadedFiles(),
        [],
        $content
    );
    $sfRequest->setMethod($method);
    $sfRequest->headers->replace($headers);
    $sfRequest->server->set('REQUEST_URI', $request->getUri());

    if (isset($headers['Host'])) {
        $sfRequest->server->set('SERVER_NAME', current($headers['Host']));
    }

    try {
        $sfResponse = $kernel->handle($sfRequest);
    } catch (\Exception $e) {
        $logger->error('Internal server error', ['error' =>

```

```

    $e->getMessage(), 'trace' => $e->getTraceAsString());
        $sfResponse = new
\Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response('Internal server error', 500);
    } catch (\Throwable $e) {
        $logger->error('Internal server error', ['error' =>
    $e->getMessage(), 'trace' => $e->getTraceAsString());
        $sfResponse = new
\Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response('Internal server error', 500);
    }

    $kernel->terminate($sfRequest, $sfResponse);
    if ($rebootKernelAfterRequest) {
        $kernel->reboot(null);
    }

    return new React\Http\Response(
        $sfResponse->getStatusCode(),
        $sfResponse->headers->all(),
        $sfResponse->getContent()
    );
});

$server->on('error', function (\Exception $e) use ($logger) {
    $logger->error('Internal server error', ['error' => $e->getMessage(),
    'trace' => $e->getTraceAsString()]);
});

$socket = new React\Socket\Server('tcp://0.0.0.0:9000', $loop);
$server->listen($socket);

$logger->info('Server running', ['addr' => 'tcp://0.0.0.0:9000']);

$loop->run();

```

Command to run the application with docker-compose:

```
cd docker/react-php && docker-compose up -d --scale php=2
```

Road Runner

[Web Server and PHP Process Manager](#). Written in Go

Pros:

- you can write a worker that initializes variables only once and continues to reuse them.

Cons:

- custom worker implementation is required.

- memory management is necessary.
- If the `--reboot-kernel-after-request` flag is used for the worker, the Symfony Kernel will reinitialize for every request. This eliminates the need for memory management.

```
#!/usr/bin/env php

<?php

use App\Kernel;
use Spiral\Goridge\SocketRelay;
use Spiral\RoadRunner\PSR7Client;
use Spiral\RoadRunner\Worker;
use Symfony\Bridge\PsrHttpMessage\Factory\DiactorosFactory;
use Symfony\Bridge\PsrHttpMessage\Factory\HttpFoundationFactory;
use Symfony\Component\Debug\Debug;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Request;

require __DIR__ . '/../config/bootstrap.php';

$env    = $_SERVER['APP_ENV'] ?? $_ENV['APP_ENV'] ?? 'dev';
$debug  = (bool)($_SERVER['APP_DEBUG'] ?? $_ENV['APP_DEBUG'] ?? ('prod' !==
$env));

if ($debug) {
    umask(0000);

    Debug::enable();
}

if ($trustedProxies = $_SERVER['TRUSTED_PROXIES'] ??
$_ENV['TRUSTED_PROXIES'] ?? false) {
    Request::setTrustedProxies(explode(',', $trustedProxies),
Request::HEADER_X_FORWARDED_ALL ^ Request::HEADER_X_FORWARDED_HOST);
}

if ($trustedHosts = $_SERVER['TRUSTED_HOSTS'] ?? $_ENV['TRUSTED_HOSTS'] ??
false) {
    Request::setTrustedHosts(explode(',', $trustedHosts));
}

$kernel = new Kernel($env, $debug);
$kernel->boot();
$rebootKernelAfterRequest = in_array('--reboot-kernel-after-request',
$argv);
$relay                = new SocketRelay('/tmp/road-runner.sock', null,
SocketRelay::SOCK_UNIX);
$psr7                  = new PSR7Client(new Worker($relay));
$httpFoundationFactory = new HttpFoundationFactory();
```

```
$diactorosFactory          = new DiactorosFactory();

while ($req = $psr7->acceptRequest()) {
    try {
        $request  = $httpFoundationFactory->createRequest($req);
        $response = $kernel->handle($request);
        $psr7->respond($diactorosFactory->createResponse($response));
        $kernel->terminate($request, $response);
        if($rebootKernelAfterRequest) {
            $kernel->reboot(null);
        }
    } catch (\Throwable $e) {
        $psr7->getWorker()->error((string)$e);
    }
}
```

Command to run the application with docker-compose:

```
cd docker/road-runner && docker-compose up -d
```

Testing

The testing was conducted using Yandex Tank. The application and Yandex Tank were on different virtual servers.

Specifications of the virtual server with the application:

Virtualization: KVM

CPU: 2 cores

RAM: 4096 MB

SSD: 50 GB

Connection: 100MBit

OS: CentOS 7 (64x)

Services:

- php-fpm
- php-ppm
- nginx-unit
- road-runner
- road-runner-reboot (with --reboot-kernel-after-request flag)
- react-php
- react-php-reboot (with --reboot-kernel-after-request flag)

For the 1000/10000 rps tests, the php-fpm-80 service was added.

The php-fpm configuration used for it was:

```
pm = dynamic
pm.max_children = 80
```

Yandex Tank decides beforehand how many times it needs to hit the target and doesn't stop until it runs out of "ammo." Depending on how quickly the service responds, the test may take longer than the time specified in the configuration. As a result, the graphs for different services may have different lengths. The slower the service responds, the longer its graph will be.

For each service and configuration, Yandex Tank ran only one test. So, the numbers may not be exact. The goal was to compare the performance of the services against each other.

100 rps

Phantom Yandex Tank configuration

```
phantom:  
  load_profile:  
    load_type: rps  
    schedule: line(1, 100, 60s) const(100, 540s)
```

Here are the links to the detailed report

- [php-fpm](#)
- [php-ppm](#)
- [nginx-unit](#)
- [road-runner](#)
- [road-runner-reboot](#)
- [react-php](#)
- [react-php-reboot](#)

Response Time Percentiles

	95%(ms)	90%(ms)	80%(ms)	50%(ms)	HTTP OK(%)	HTTP OK(count)
php-fpm	9.9	6.3	4.35	3.59	100	57030
php-ppm	9.4	6	3.88	3.16	100	57030
nginx-unit	11	6.6	4.43	3.69	100	57030
road-runner	8.1	5.1	3.53	2.92	100	57030
road-runner-reboot	12	8.6	5.3	3.85	100	57030
react-php	8.5	4.91	3.29	2.74	100	57030
react-php-reboot	13	8.5	5.5	3.95	100	57030

Monitoring

	cpu median(%)	cpu max(%)	memory median(MB)	memory max(MB)
php-fpm	9.15	12.58	880.32	907.97
php-ppm	7.08	13.68	901.72	913.80
nginx-unit	9.56	12.54	923.02	943.90
road-runner	5.57	8.61	992.71	1,001.46
road-runner-reboot	9.18	12.67	848.43	870.26
react-php	4.53	6.58	1,004.68	1,009.91
react-php-reboot	9.61	12.67	885.92	892.52

Charts

Chart 1.1 Average Response Time per Second

Chart 1.2 Average CPU Load per Second

Chart 1.3 Average Memory Usage per Second

500 rps

Phantom Yandex Tank configuration

```
phantom:  
  load_profile:  
    load_type: rps  
    schedule: line(1, 500, 60s) const(500, 540s)
```

Here are the links to the detailed report

- [php-fpm](#)
- [php-ppm](#)
- [nginx-unit](#)
- [road-runner](#)
- [road-runner-reboot](#)
- [react-php](#)
- [react-php-reboot](#)

Response Time Percentiles

	95%(ms)	90%(ms)	80%(ms)	50%(ms)	HTTP OK(%)	HTTP OK(count)
php-fpm	13	8.4	5.3	3.69	100	285030
php-ppm	15	9	4.72	3.24	100	285030
nginx-unit	12	8	5.5	3.93	100	285030
road-runner	9.6	6	3.71	2.83	100	285030
road-runner-reboot	14	11	7.1	4.45	100	285030
react-php	9.3	5.8	3.57	2.68	100	285030
react-php-reboot	15	12	7.2	4.21	100	285030

Monitoring

	cpu median(%)	cpu max(%)	memory median(MB)	memory max(MB)
php-fpm	41.68	48.33	1,006.06	1,015.09
php-ppm	33.90	48.90	1,046.32	1,055.00
nginx-unit	42.13	47.92	1,006.67	1,015.73
road-runner	24.08	28.06	1,035.86	1,044.58
road-runner-reboot	46.23	52.04	939.63	948.08
react-php	19.57	23.42	1,049.83	1,060.26
react-php-reboot	41.30	47.89	957.01	958.56

Charts

Chart 2.1 Average Response Time per Second

Chart 2.2 Average CPU Load per Second

Chart 2.3 Average Memory Usage per Second

1000 rps

Phantom Yandex Tank configuration

```
phantom:  
  load_profile:  
    load_type: rps  
    schedule: line(1, 1000, 60s) const(1000, 60s)
```

Here are the links to the detailed report

- [php-fpm](#)
- [php-fpm-80](#)
- [php-ppm](#)
- [nginx-unit](#)
- [road-runner](#)
- [road-runner-reboot](#)
- [react-php](#)
- [react-php-reboot](#)

Response Time Percentiles

	95%(ms)	90%(ms)	80%(ms)	50%(ms)	HTTP OK(%)	HTTP OK(count)
php-fpm	11050	11050	9040	195	80.67	72627
php-fpm-80	3150	1375	1165	152	99.85	89895
php-ppm	2785	2740	2685	2545	100	90030
nginx-unit	98	80	60	21	100	90030
road-runner	27	15	7.1	3.21	100	90030
road-runner-reboot	1110	1100	1085	1060	100	90030
react-php	23	13	5.6	2.86	100	90030
react-php-reboot	28	24	19	11	100	90030

Monitoring

	cpu median(%)	cpu max(%)	memory median(MB)	memory max(MB)
php-fpm	12.66	78.25	990.16	1,006.56
php-fpm-80	83.78	91.28	746.01	937.24
php-ppm	66.16	91.20	1,088.74	1,102.92
nginx-unit	78.11	88.77	1,010.15	1,062.01
road-runner	42.93	54.23	1,010.89	1,068.48
road-runner-reboot	77.64	85.66	976.44	1,044.05
react-php	36.39	46.31	1,018.03	1,088.23
react-php-reboot	72.11	81.81	911.28	961.62

Charts

Response time

Chart 3.1 Average Response Time per Second

Response time

Chart 3.2 Average Response Time per Second (без php-fpm, php-ppm, road-runner-reboot)

CPU usage

Chart 3.3 Average CPU Load per Second

Chart 3.4 Average Memory Usage per Second

10000 rps

Phantom Yandex Tank configuration

```
phantom:  
  load_profile:  
    load_type: rps  
    schedule: line(1, 10000, 30s) const(10000, 30s)
```

Here are the links to the detailed report

- [php-fpm](#)
- [php-fpm-80](#)
- [php-ppm](#)
- [nginx-unit](#)
- [road-runner](#)
- [road-runner-reboot](#)
- [react-php](#)
- [react-php-reboot](#)

Response Time Percentiles

	95%(ms)	90%(ms)	80%(ms)	50%(ms)	HTTP OK(%)	HTTP OK(count)
php-fpm	11050	11050	11050	1880	70.466	317107
php-fpm-80	3260	3140	1360	1145	99.619	448301
php-ppm	2755	2730	2695	2605	100	450015
nginx-unit	1020	1010	1000	980	100	450015
road-runner	640	630	615	580	100	450015
road-runner-reboot	1130	1120	1110	1085	100	450015
react-php	1890	1090	1045	58	99.996	449996
react-php-reboot	3480	3070	1255	91	99.72	448753

Monitoring

	cpu median(%)	cpu max(%)	memory median(MB)	memory max(MB)
php-fpm	5.57	79.35	984.47	998.78
php-fpm-80	85.05	92.19	936.64	943.93
php-ppm	66.86	82.41	1,089.31	1,097.41
nginx-unit	86.14	93.94	1,067.71	1,069.52
road-runner	73.41	82.72	1,129.48	1,134.00
road-runner-reboot	80.32	86.29	982.69	984.80
react-php	73.76	82.18	1,101.71	1,105.06
react-php-reboot	85.77	91.92	975.85	978.42

Charts

Chart 4.1 Average Response Time per Second

Chart 4.2 Average Response Time per Second (без php-fpm, php-ppm)

Chart 4.3 Average CPU Load per Second

Memory usage

Chart 4.4 Average Memory Usage per Second

Summary

Here are the graphs showing how the performance characteristics of services change depending on the load. When viewing the graphs, keep in mind that not all services responded to 100% of the requests.

Chart 5.1 95% response time percentile

Chart 5.2 95% response time percentile (without php-fpm)

Chart 5.3 Maximum CPU load

Chart 5.4 Maximum memory usage

In my opinion, the optimal solution (without changing the code) is the Nginx Unit process manager. It shows good performance in response times and has support from the company. In any case, the approach to development and the tools should be chosen individually, depending on your load, server resources, and the capabilities of your developers.